

Analysis of the Long Fibularis during gait in individuals with Chronic Ankle Instability - A systematic review.

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Abstract:

Among the dysfunctions occurring in the body, 77% are in the lower limbs, of these lesions, 39% occur in the knee and ankle joints. It is common in the literature studies that link Chronic Ankle Instability (CAI) to tests and treatments with the Long Fibular Muscle, however, there are few studies aimed at analyzing gait function associated with the quality of activation or the health of this muscle. Initially this study aims to correlate, through reviews in the literature, the common aspects between the three aspects: Chronic Ankle Instability; Contractile alterations of the Long Fibular muscle and gait alterations, seeking common incidences between them. It can later link postural changes with these dysfunctions. In order to carry out this bibliographic review, we searched for articles in PedRo, Medline and PubMed databases. Of these searches 58 (n = 58) articles published since 2006 were found, containing literary reviews and field research. Through the searches in the literature, 37 articles were added to this study, of which 28 (90.3%) had publication years between 2008 and 2017. Of the authors who evaluate their progress, most use Postural Control as an evaluation basis Or method of intervention of the researches. There is still a shortage of studies linking these aspects, and there is a need for more research with emphasis on posture and joint biomechanics and its afferent effects; As well as more elaborate methodologies on the effects of proprioceptive training on patients with Chronic Ankle Instability.

Keywords: ankle; gait; peroneus longus.

Introduction:

Among the musculoskeletal changes that occur in the body, 77% occur in the lower limbs, of these injuries, 39% occur in the knee and ankle joints. The ankle is the second most common site of injury in sports (Fong, 2007), and 40% of the affected structures develop chronic joint instability (Kaminski, 2002). Traumatic recurrences in this structure can lead to irreversible changes in ankle ligament flexibility (Webster and Gribble, 2010).

Delahunt et. al. (2010) referred to Chronic Ankle Instability (CAI) as the symptoms of repetitive ankle sprains and episodes of instability that occur more than a year after the initial sprain. Chronic ankle joint instability is among the main causes of functional limitations and significantly increases the chances of recurrent ankle sprains (Kaminski, 2002), as well as causing pain, local muscle weakness, proprioceptive deficits, balance difficulties, and functional limitation (Arnold, 2009).

Brent et. al. (2011) in their work analyzed the quality of life perception of individuals with CAI and concluded that joint functional limitation causes a deficit in the outcome of this index, indicating the importance of work for the functional adequacy of this joint. Since dysfunctions in this structure cause changes in the individual's gait.

The treatment plans for this dysfunction include proprioceptive stimulation training, static balance exercises, manual therapy to assist in positioning and stabilization of the joint, motor control, and strengthening of the long fibular and other evertors. (Morrison; LEE)

It is common in the literature to link Chronic Ankle Instability to tests and treatments in the distal lateral structures of the lower limb, mainly with the Long Fibular muscle. However, studies aimed at analyzing the gait function associated with the quality of activation or health of this muscle in individuals with CAI are scarce.

When we refer to gait, the individuals studied present a decrease in dorsiflexion (Brown, 2011), showing relationships with the lateral musculature of the lower limb. Delahunt et al. 2006, report a greater inversion positioning during the swing phase in these

patients, remaining longer supported on the lateral region of the feet, thus favoring the recurrence of sprains.

Initially, this study aims to correlate, through literature reviews, the common aspects between the three aspects: Chronic Ankle Instability; contractile changes of the Long Fibular muscle, and changes in gait, and later link postural changes with these dysfunctions, given that imbalances in the lower limbs can generate compensations in the chain for the rest of the body.

Methodology:

For this literature review, articles were searched in the PedRo, Medline, and PubMed databases, using the keywords: "Peroneus Longus; Ankle sprain; Instability; Gait; Walk."

The articles found will be selected according to the year of publication (2006 to 2017); congruence with the topic addressed, and relevance to this review. Articles that do not meet these criteria will be excluded from the search.

Results:

From these searches, 58 (n=58) articles were found, including literature reviews and field research published from 2006 onwards. Through literature searches, 37 articles were added to this study, with 28 (90.3%) published between 2008 and 2017. Twenty-one evaluated articles were excluded from the study for not meeting the inclusion criteria.

Of the included articles, 91.8% relate the Long Fibular Muscle to CAI; 16.2% analyze CAI with gait or other functional activity; and 5.4% cite in their work the relationship of the Long Fibular in CAI during gait.

Discussion:

Given the content found in the literature regarding the topic addressed, the first key point we can find is the consensus among research on the relationship of Long Fibular Muscle activation with Chronic Ankle Instability, indicating a longer response time of the muscle contraction in individuals with CAI. According to Donovan (2012), those with Chronic Ankle Instability should have significant deficiencies in four aspects: range of

motion, muscle strength, balance, and functional activities. These points serve as markers of this dysfunction and should be considered during evaluation for studies and treatments.

Donovan, Hart, and Hertel (2014) evaluated the activation of lower limb muscles of 15 adults with Chronic Ankle Instability by electromyography, subjecting them to footwear that caused joint instability during gait and found a significant deficit in Long Fibular activation.

Feger (2015) conducted a comparative study with 50 adults, comparing the activation results of lower limb muscles during gait between patients with CAI and a control group, which showed a longer muscle activation time in the first group compared to the second.

A significant number of studies aim to analyze treatments for this dysfunction, and among the main methods used are proprioceptive stimulation training, static balance exercises, manual therapy to assist in joint positioning and stabilization, motor control, and strengthening of Long Fibular and other evertors. Among those gathered for this review, all reported an improvement in Long Fibular muscle activation when evaluated by electromyography, thus supporting the essentiality of a treatment plan with an emphasis, among others, on improving the muscular quality of this muscle.

In 2010, Cloak and colleagues conducted a controlled study with 38 dancers who reported ankle instability and had sprained at least once, subjecting them to a six-week vibratory platform treatment program, where they found relevant improvements in the intervention group's balance. However, regarding the effects on the Long Fibular muscle, there were no changes in the results.

In another study, Mckeon et.al. (2008) examined the effects of a four-week balance training program on 29 adults with chronic ankle instability, in addition to the effects on the mechanical properties of the lateral ligaments. Based on the results found, the authors concluded that there were significant changes in the hindfoot movements in inversion and eversion movements.

Hiller (2011) conducted a literature review analyzing the characteristics found in individuals with recurrent ankle sprains and concluded that the mechanics of this recurrent dysfunction cause radiographic changes in the talus, changes in gait during gait, and increased activation time in stabilization. However, there is not enough data referring to functional changes and ranges of motion of this joint, unlike what happens with Chronic Ankle Instability patients, where, according to the literature, ranges of motion are altered mainly in dorsiflexion. Similarly, Drewes (2009), in his work on CAI, used 40 volunteers in a controlled comparative study and identified a deficiency in dorsiflexion as a risk factor for recurrent sprains in these individuals.

Studies that aim to evaluate functional and gait issues in these individuals have a consensus on important aspects to define the real link between key points in this research. The majority of studies analyze aspects such as postural control, postural stability, and gait dynamics, among others. This indicates that authors tend to naturally link dysfunction in the Fibular Longus to chronic ankle instability and thus to postural and gait deficiencies.

According to Brow (2011), constant ankle instability can lead to joint complications resulting in osteoarthritis. Based on the conclusions of the above authors, we can define the importance of early therapeutic intervention in patients suffering from recurrent sprains in order to prevent the progression of dysfunction and future functional complications.

Seung-min Nam et al. (2016) evaluated the effects of balance training in 28 adults with chronic ankle instability and found better responses in Fibular Longus muscle activation through electromyography.

Ki-Jong Kim et al. (2014) divided 30 individuals with chronic ankle instability into three groups: "A," control group; "B," lower limb muscle strengthening; and "C," muscle strengthening associated with proprioceptive training. Based on ankle joint function, it was concluded that groups "B" and "C" obtained significant results compared to the control group, and the group where proprioceptive training was associated with strengthening obtained relevant results compared to strength training alone.

Moreno et al. (2015) conducted a randomized study with 27 people with chronic ankle instability, testing the effects of Trigger Point and Dry Needling techniques associated with proprioceptive exercises and found greater efficacy when compared to isolated proprioceptive exercises.

Barlow, Donovan, Hart, and Hertel (2015) tested the muscle activation of 50 adults undergoing ankle bracing stabilization. The results collected from electromyography showed changes in neuromuscular activity of Fibular Longus and other muscles, which could later facilitate recurrence of ankle sprain.

The literature shows different points regarding the concept of proprioception in optimizing Fibular Longus muscle quality. In general, it is pointed out that proprioceptive training brings benefits to ankle-related structures but does not have significant effects on range of motion and functional joint quality. In addition, another important factor found in studies such as those by Donovan et al. (2016) and Ferger et al. (2015) is the functional change in ankle movements and, in particular, changes in gait cycles of these individuals. It was found that they remain supported for a longer time by the lateral region of the feet during the support phase, have a greater inversion position during the swing phase, and a decrease in dorsiflexion, favoring recurrence of ankle sprain.

Baur et al. (2011) evaluated the neuromuscular activity of Fibular Longus in 99 runners with reports of overuse injury who were placed under foot orthoses during walking. Based on the collected data, they reported an increase in early activation of Fibular Longus before and after the intervention. They suggest that this fact motivates joint stabilization from proprioceptive and muscular activation changes structurally adapted in individuals with this dysfunction during gait.

In order to analyze the motor responses of postural organization during movement and gait in individuals with Chronic Ankle Instability (CAI), Hass et.al. (2010) studied 5 men and 15 women with CAI during gait and vertical jump movements, and found alterations and declines in postural planning and organization. Also, in their review on the neuromuscular relationship with chronic ankle instability, Delahunt (2007) concluded that it is of paramount importance to include postural control exercises in the treatment of this dysfunction.

In parallel, McKeon and Hertel (2008) subjected 32 individuals with CAI to a comparative study with healthy individuals on spatial and balance tests to detect postural control alterations, and observed a significant deficit in the results when they were tested with their eyes closed, which did not occur with eyes open, suggesting a great need for postural reorganization strategies dependent on the visual stimulus of these individuals.

During this review, Postural Control was used by several authors as an evaluative factor to qualify the functional quality of gait, that is, when the goal is to analyze the quality of gait and balance of individuals, static or dynamic postural control is commonly evaluated. Similarly, postural control training is used as a therapeutic intervention to provide results on CAI. However, there is a need for further studies on this concept, particularly studies that analyze the relationship of fibular dysfunctions directly with postural control, leading us to expand the topic to areas of Posturology and correlate their methods with results in Chronic Ankle Instability.

Conclusion:

The articles cited in this review that analyze individuals with Chronic Ankle Instability almost unanimously point out in their research the relationships of the evertors, mainly the Fibularis Longus, with CAI, however, proprioceptive training is not a consensus regarding its effects. Of the authors who evaluate gait, a large part uses Postural Control as an evaluative basis or intervention method for their research. There is still a scarcity of studies linking these aspects, and there is a need for more research with emphasis on posture and joint biomechanics and their afferent effects, as well as more elaborate methodologies on the effects of proprioceptive training in individuals with Chronic Ankle Instability.

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